

SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein and Reactivation of human herpesvirus 6 and 7

Version 1

Description

The project aims to understand the host-pathogen interaction between SARS-CoV-2 Spike proteins and the human host, hoping to characterize host factors that can induce HHV-6/HHV-7 reactivation. This will help us in dissecting out molecular pathways behind HHV reactivation and characterize further mechanisms of host-virus interactions, particularly focusing on immune modulations.

Data will be generated from single-cell RNA-seq (scRNA-seq) and scSLAM-seq, mass spectroscopy experiments, imaging, and functional assays.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

lzp-2025/1-0130

Researchers

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0737)

Organizations

Riga Stradiņš University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein and Reactivation of human herpesvirus 6 and 7

Description:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: lzp-2025/1-0130

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

RSU DMP Template

Template: RSU DMP Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The project aims to understand the host-pathogen interaction between SARS-CoV-2 Spike proteins and the human host hoping to characterize host factors that can induce HHV-6/HHV-7 reactivation. This will help us in dissecting out molecular pathways behind HHV reactivation and characterize further mechanisms of host-virus interactions, particularly focusing on immune modulations.

Data will be generated from single-cell RNA-seq (scRNA-seq) and scSLAM-seq, mass spectroscopy experiments, imaging, and functional assays.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

- RSU researchers (Immunology, Virology, Bioinformatics)
- International herpesvirus and long-COVID researchers

- Students working on virology, sequencing, organoids
- Clinical virology / translational medicine collaborators
- Public and patient organizations interested in long-COVID mechanisms
- Bioinformaticians (scRNA-seq, scSLAM-seq)

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Observation data
- Ratings
- Other

Omics data (single-cell RNA-seq, scSLAM-seq, miRNA-seq) • Proteomics (IP-MS interactome) • Imaging data (fluorescence microscopy, confocal, organoid imaging) • Molecular biology data (PCR, Northern blots) • Processed data (count matrices, metadata tables) • Protocol-related textual data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- PNG
- JSON

- JPG

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

3-5 TB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Yes. The following search keywords will be provided. SARS-CoV-2 Spike, HHV-6, HHV-7, reactivation, miRNA, scSLAM-seq, interactome, organoids, long-COVID.

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- Codebook

- ReadMe file

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

An International standard will be used to document the datasets.

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Yes. All formats (FASTQ, CSV, TIFF, TXT) will be widely accessible using open-source tools after publication of the manuscripts.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Statistics: R, Python

- Imaging: FIJI/ImageJ
- Sequencing: Cell Ranger, GRAND-SLAM

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Standard, internationally acceptable texts like Gene ontology (GO), RefSeq, Cell Ontology, Uberon for organoids will be used.

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

CC BY-NC-SA

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

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2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

Yes

Expected 1 year until the manuscript is published.

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2027-12-24

The data will be made available to re-use immediately after publication of the associated manuscript.

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

Covered by project budget + RSU infrastructure support (RSU Dataverse).

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

Riga Stradins University

Riga Stradiņš University (RSU) — primary data controller

- RSU Science Centre, MVI — data processing and storage

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project? Which person will be the data manager responsible for the correct processing of data in the project, staff training, and maintenance of the data management plan?

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3.1.5 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors-researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other persons who will work with the data for this study)?

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Comment:

- PhD student — spike expression, reactivation assays, organoids, cell culture, imaging support,
- Postdoc — scRNA-seq, scSLAM-seq processing
- PI — oversight, data validation

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

The detailed methodology for generating or processing data will be provided within the published manuscript associated with the data.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

- RSU MVI secure servers for raw/processed data
- Data retained for 5 years after project end unless required longer by regulation

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

Data will be deleted in accordance with the procedures .

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long-term preservation and curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

No

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

No

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

Anonymising data

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